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Review of Jean-Denis Vigne, François Briois and Jean Guilaine (eds.), 2023. *Klimonas. An early Pre-Pottery Neolithic village in Cyprus*. Gallia Préhistoire. International Supplement 1. Paris: CNRS Éditions. ISBN 978-2271139535, 632 pages, € 79.

The early Pre-Pottery Neolithic (PPN) site of Klimonas on Cyprus was the first PPNA-affiliated site to be discovered on the island and the second – after Asprokremnos (McCartney *et al.* 2007) – to be excavated, this by a French team led by Jean-Denis Vigne, François Briois and Jean Guilaine between 2009 and 2016. Dating to a few decades centred on 8,800 calBCE, the site is, on current evidence, the second-largest Neolithic site on Cyprus after Khirokitia, and a precursor of the nearby PPNB-affiliated site of Shillourokambos (Guilaine *et al.* 2011, 2021) which was excavated by the same team between 1992 and 2004. With 38 buildings or the remains thereof excavated, including a 10m-diameter communal building of northern-Levantine type which alone yielded more than three tonnes of flint, 21,426 animal bone fragments, 11,600 phytoliths, 5,225 charred seeds, 1,299 ornamental objects and 576 charcoal fragments recovered, Klimonas is of critical importance to our understanding of the origins and evolution of the Cypriot Neolithic and its relations with the adjacent mainland. It offers a short-lived snapshot of the still-shadowy two millennia (10,500–8,500 calBCE) between the Epipalaeolithic represented primarily by Akrotiri, but now also Aspros, Mazotos, Nissi Beach, Pakhtomena and Roudias, and the Early PPNB of Mylouthkia, Shillourokambos and Tenta. This impressive book and its numerous easy-to-use online appendices comprise the final publication of the 2009–2016 excavations at Klimonas. The team are to be congratulated on the prompt, professional and detailed discharge of their responsibilities. The resulting volume is a benchmark in Cypriot and Near Eastern Neolithic studies.

The book is divided logically into six parts. Part one consists of two introductory chapters on the insular and mainland context of the PPNA, the site's location, and the methods employed during its excavation. The latter made heavy use of open-area, mechanical surface stripping, followed by stratigraphic excavation of exposed features and considerable wet sieving of deposits. As a result, significant horizontal exposures were obtained. Part two presents the stratigraphic and architectural data from the excavations, with three chapters focused on different sectors of the site and a fourth dedicated to the aforementioned communal building and its immediate surroundings. Two additional chapters cover the geomor-

phology of the site and its post-PPN – primarily Ceramic Neolithic – utilisation. Given the presence of at least one Sotira-culture structure on the site's middle terrace and extensive Ceramic Neolithic-period mining out of the PPNA structures, presumably, to recover cob building material for re-use, the three pages of text devoted to the latter chapter falls disappointingly short of the generally impressive level of detail seen elsewhere in the volume. Part three, titled *The Village and its Evolution*, seeks to contextualize part two. It contains chapters on the geoarchaeology of Klimonas's mud architecture and on the critical topic of chronology, specifically the date and duration of the village's occupation. Three further chapters very usefully summarize specific aspects of the architecture, including caches and hoards in foundation trenches and the bases of walls and within the structural make-up of peripheral benches. This demonstrates conclusively the utility of completely excavating structural elements in the Neolithic context, with the recovery of normally hidden information on the intangible symbolic attributes of buildings arguably outweighing site-conservation considerations that might preclude excavation to ground zero. The material culture of Klimonas is dealt with clearly and succinctly in eight chapters in part four.

The fifth part of the volume, *Bio-Archaeological Evidence*, is perhaps the book's highlight, with no less than eight of its eleven chapters dealing with different aspects of the site's faunal remains. Given the extraordinarily limited biodiversity of Cyprus in the early 9th millennium, with only four mammalian taxa currently represented, this is no small achievement.

The Klimonas faunal assemblage was absolutely dominated by the newly described – in Chapter 30 – but now-extinct Cypriot wild boar. Given that this had clearly been brought to Cyprus by humans by the 11th millennium calBCE, as evidenced by its presence at Akrotiri, the intensity and multi-faceted nature of human-pig relations within the context of the Klimonas hunting economy brings to mind the longstanding and – at the time they were made – quite controversial claims of Rosenberg *et al.* (1998) for management of wild boar in the upper Tigris valley during the mid-10th millennium calBCE at terminal Epipalaeolithic Hallan Çemi. It is pleasing to see the Klimonas data evaluated here in light of a thoughtful re-examination of these important claims. A whole chapter is devoted to the possible symbolic value of wild boar to the inhabitants of Klimonas, making a compelling argument that aspects of contemporary aurochs-focused symbolism on the mainland were perhaps expressed through the medium of boar on Cyprus, cattle being absent on the island until – on current evidence – the mid-9th millennium calBCE. The book concludes with its sixth part, a magisterial summary chapter that neatly draws together the main conclusions of the preceding four parts and evaluates them in the context of both the Cypriot Neolithic and Levantine PPNA. For those without the time to work through the 600-page volume in its entirety, this chapter, entitled *The Neolithic Village of Klimonas: Technical, Social and Symbolic Aspects; Insularity and Connectivity*, is without doubt the place to start.

The level of detail provided in this book is remarkable and derives from the systematic application of what are really quite straightforward methods on a scrappy, poorly preserved site. Indeed, it's hard to see how much more data could have been squeezed out of the excavations. In this context, it is particularly welcome to see technology being applied as an enabler of excavation objectives rather than as an end in its own right. The volume continues the long-standing Cypriot tradition of high-quality publication of Neolithic sites, started by Dikaios (1953) at Khirokitia. Quite aside from describing the Klimonas data, their interpretation in this book draws several conclusions that are of critical importance to scholars working both on Cyprus and in the Near East. First, with the exception of a single mouse tooth of possible Anatolian type (Vigne *et al.* 2023: 473-74), nothing at Klimonas calls into question the assertion made first by Peltenburg *et al.* (2001) that the strongest cultural affiliations of Pre-Pottery Neolithic of Cyprus lie with the middle and upper Euphrates and Tigris valleys and the Jezireh region of modern Syria and Iraq, with the unfortunate caveat that to this day almost nothing is known of that period on the Cilician and northern Levantine coasts. Second, despite the not-insubstantial

extent of Klimonas – estimated at between 5,500 and 9,000m² – it would appear that comparatively few structures were occupied at any one time, with the village being occupied for no more than three or four generations. This has profound implications for population estimates and reconstructions of communal organisation, requiring all of us working on large Neolithic sites to rigorously test the evidence for contemporaneity of adjacent structures. Third, the faunal and botanical data from Klimonas point to the existence of considerable complexity in human relations with the insular natural world before the onset of domestication in the mid-9th millennium calBCE, to say nothing of some surprising twists when it finally gathered pace.

About plant economies, the evidence from Klimonas strongly suggests that einkorn and emmer wheat had been imported to the island from the mainland by the early 9th-millennium calBCE and were cultivated around the site, along with barley that may have been of local origin. The nature of the cereal remains at Klimonas didn't allow for the determination of their wild or domestic status on morphological grounds. However, domestic forms of all three are known from the mid-9th millennium calBCE Mylouthkia (Murray 2003). About faunal economies, the presence of wild boar at Akrotiri demonstrates that this taxon had been transported to Cyprus by humans by the 11th millennium calBCE, most likely from northern Mesopotamia and/ or the upper Tigris valley (Vigne *et al.* 2023: 522 [*cf.* Rosenberg *et al.* 1998]). This was, in all probability, done to stock the island with a huntable food resource, which was – to the extent that the limited quantity of available data allowed us to surmise – exploited to the near-exclusion of other animal resources for the next two millennia. As an aside, Chapter 33 sensibly discusses the absence of marine food resources at Klimonas in the context of the well-known ichthyophobia exhibited by Indigenous Tasmanians in the three-and-a-half millennia before European settlement, which is thought to have been an economic maladaptation facilitated by minimal demographic and resource pressure (Jones 1978) – as seems also to have been the case on Neolithic Cyprus. Returning to wild boar, a vital contribution of this volume is the assertion, backed up by a detailed morphometric study, that when domestic pigs first appear in the Cypriot faunal record in the mid-9th millennium calBCE, they represent local domestication of the endemic Cypriot wild boar rather than the introduction of domestic pigs from the mainland. As was the case in so many mainland animal domestications (*e.g.*, goat; sheep [Zeder 2024]), it now seems clear that pig domestication on Cyprus evolved out of a long tradition of hunting the wild progenitor. The emergence of Cyprus as an independent centre of

animal domestication returns ecological agency to the island's Neolithic inhabitants, who can no longer be regarded as wholly passive recipients of food-producing innovation from elsewhere. By highlighting these issues and others, the book forces us to think critically about the much wider issue of how hunter-foragers may have manipulated, shaped and 'improved' their landscapes to build sustainable non-domestic economies over prolonged periods (*cf.* Sutton and Walshe 2021).

With a book of this quality, it feels almost churlish to highlight deficiencies. Objectivity requires it however, although it may be noted at the outset that where these exist, they relate more to details of interpretation than to failures of data presentation. It's also worth emphasising that the volume is already enormous, even without its online appendices. A strong case can be made, therefore, that the editors made the correct decision to leave debate and refinement of the invaluable data presented to subsequent articles and symposia.

The chrono-cultural attribution of Klimonas to the PPNA warrants careful consideration, for although this is undeniable on material-culture grounds, the highly late occurrence of Klimonas within the normative span of the northern Levantine PPNA (~9,700-8,800 calBCE) raises several issues. Foremost amongst these is the fact, demonstrated by recent data from the western margins of the Jordanian *badia*, that the Early PPNB emerged here as early as 8,900-8,800 calBCE, that is to say as early as – if not earlier than – in the middle Euphrates valley (Fujii 2024). This allows a conceptual link to be drawn between PPNA-affiliated Klimonas and the last PPNA complexes on the mainland, such as that observed at Wadi Faynan 16 Phase 3 (Mithen *et al.* 2018: 650-52), which are now known to have co-existed directly alongside the nascent Early PPNB for several centuries. The problem that arises is that the volume tends to discuss Klimonas in the context of a mainland PPNA world that had, in places, disappeared and was elsewhere, fast disappearing by the time the site was established. This is the earliest documentation of the recidivist tendencies that would go on to dominate Cypriot prehistory until at least the mid-4th millennium calBCE (*cf.* Clarke and Wasse 2019), and it is a matter of regret that these complex issues aren't discussed in more detail here.

Another consequence of the book's tendency to look to the mainland PPNA for comparanda is that this notionally synchronic but slightly backward-looking approach in places discourages exploration of several fascinating diachronic issues that emerge so clearly from the beautifully presented Klimonas data. When considering what the legacy of Klimonas might have been for later Cypriot Neolithic societies (Vigne

et al. 2023: 594), the volume inexplicably skirts around the long archaeological sequence at Tenta. Here, the earliest of the three above-ground, top-of-site communal buildings – 7.5m-diameter structure 36 – displays several similarities with the Klimonas communal building, including a central post and a series of peripheral stakes close to the inner face of the perimeter wall (Todd 1987: 88, 109), yet these aren't mentioned. Given the evidence now emerging from the southern Levant for the concurrence in close geographical proximity of terminal PPNA and Early PPNB cultural entities, the possibility that early-phase Tenta might represent a survival of earlier Klimonas-affiliated lifeways, whilst other parts of the island were enthusiastically embracing the Early PPNB, at least warrants consideration. In a similar vein, another consequence of the notionally synchronic approach to comparanda is that it leaves little scope for discussion of the well-documented continuation of behaviours documented at Klimonas into the 7th and 6th millennia calBCE, whether on Cyprus, at Khirokitia, or further afield, as in the Jordanian *badia* (Wasse *et al.* 2022: 261-62, 2024: 8, 11-16). Whilst detailed discussion of the latter clearly lies beyond the scope of the volume, it remains the case that the mainland late Epipalaeolithic and PPNA cultural complexes which so influenced Klimonas also had a profound impact on other areas of the Near East in which agriculturalist PPNB traditions were less embedded. The trends seen at Klimonas are, therefore, to some extent, nested within a much broader context of non-PPNB recidivism, which might have been mentioned.

Although the interpretations put forward in the book are generally logical and evidence-based, there are a few occasions on which the data are stretched almost to breaking point. An excellent example of this concerns the reconstruction of the Klimonas architectural norm as comprising a 360-degree cob wall within a neatly cut, curvilinear foundation trench. The problem with this is that the southern, downslope sides of the Klimonas buildings are typically badly eroded owing to the slopes of the terraces on which they're constructed. Consequently, minimal evidence for upstanding architecture survives here, resulting that architectural reconstructions for 360-degree walling are necessarily based more on assumption and extrapolation than on hard data. This ought not to be a problem, were it not for the fact that peripheral stake- and post-holes are typically absent or rare in upslope foundation trenches but were more commonly used to support the downslope sides of buildings (Vigne *et al.* 2023: 222). This, coupled with the frequent shallowness and, more pertinently, the narrow width of many downslope foundation trenches, has led the authors to propose that downslope walls may have had a different architectural function than upslope ones (Vigne *et al.*

2023: 223). However, as there is little physical evidence for the existence of the posited downslope walls, the possibility that structures were largely or in part open to the south – with ‘foundation’ trenches here fulfilling a role more akin to delineation – might perhaps have been subjected to more rigorous testing than has been the case (e.g., Vigne *et al.* 2023: 111). In this context, it will be recalled that Natufian shelters are typically reconstructed as being open on one side.

These are minor quibbles, however, and certainly detract less from the volume than its lack of an index or occasional typographic errors in the extensive bibliography. Overall, this book is a nicely produced, well-written and beautifully illustrated triumph for which the editors and contributors deserve congratulations. Not only is it a milestone in our understanding of the Cypriot PPN and Mediterranean-island prehistory more generally, to say nothing of being a self-evident benchmark in how to approach the publication process, any scholar of the Near Eastern Neolithic will find much food for thought in its 600 pages – and may well be surprised at what they discover there.

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